

Holliday junction recognition protein (HJURP) : Machine learning discoveries of 2^{nd} order synergy in Meningiomas

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Abstract

Background : HJURP is a mitogenic protein that is a chaperone protein of histone H3. The gene is located on chromosome 2q37.1 and is involved in nucleosome composition in the mitotic region, forming a three-dimensional crystal structure with Centromere Protein A (CENPA) and the histone 4 complex. Further, it is involved in the recruitment and assembly of centromere and kinetochore and plays a key role in stabilizing the chromosome structure of tumor cells, and its dysfunction may contribute to tumorigenesis (Li et al. [1]). Meningiomas are the most common intracranial primary neoplasm in adults. Patel et al. [2] analyzed 160 tumors from all 3 World Health Organization (WHO) grades (I through III) using clinical, gene expression, and sequencing data and using unsupervised clustering analysis identified 3 molecular types (A, B, and C) that reliably predicted recurrence. Further, these groups did not directly correlate with the WHO grading system, which classifies more than half of the tumors in the most aggressive molecular type as benign. **Issue** : Increasing evidence point to the fact that meningioma classification and grading, that is based on histopathology does not always accurately predict tumor aggressiveness and recurrence behaviour and knowledge of the underlying biology of the treatment resistant meningiomas and the impact of genetic alterations in these tumors, is lacking. At the current stage more genomic studies are required to unravel the role of other genes and their interations with other genetic factors. **Resolution** : In a recently published work Sinha [3], a frame work of a search engine was developed which can rank combinations of factors (genes/proteins) in a signaling pathway. Adapting this search engine to the Meningioma dataset, i present here 2^{nd} order combinations of HJURP, some of which have been known to exist via wet lab experiments, but many are yet to be tested. The reveals combinations might help oncologists/biologists test possible hypotheses that might be the causing factors in meningioma. Further, in my limited grasp, if proven true, the combinations revealed by the search engine might pave way for development of gene based therapies aimed at resolving pathological issues related to meningiomas.

*ML dicoveries of HJURP synergy in Meningiomas

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1. Introduction

1.1. Meningioma

Meningiomas are the most common intracranial primary neoplasm in adults. They arise from the arachnoid cap cells. These arachnoid cap cells are specialized cells that make up the arachnoid mater (one of the three protective membranes covering the brain and spinal cord). The arachnoid mater is one of the three meninges. The other two that constitute the meninges are dura mater and pia mater.

1.1.1. World Health Organization (WHO) classification

The meningiomas are classified into three grades by WHO under the Central Nervous System tumours, namely, Grade I (benign), Grade II (atypical) and Grade III (anaplastic/malignant), based on histopathology or subtype (Louis et al. [5]). As of 2021, there exists 12 histopathological meningioma subtypes according to a mini-review by Torp

et al. [6]. They are meningothelial, fibrous, transitional, psammomatous, angioma-tous, microcystic, secretory, lymphoplasmacyte-rich, atypical, chordoid, clear cell and anaplastic (malignant) meningioma.

1.1.2. Historical perspective

Czarnetzki et al. [7] investigated a skull that was excavated at Steinheim/Murr (Baden-Wurttemberg, Germany) and consisted of a well preserved plagiocephalic cranium, with most of the facial skeleton intact. Their results of stratigraphical dating suggested the fossil specimen of *Homo steinheimensis*, was about 3,65,000 years old. In the fossile, they found that several features of the inner cranial table were consistent with a diagnosis of meningioma.

As documented in Okonkwo and Laws Jr [8], in 1614, Felix Plater, Professor of Medicine, issued a case report from the University of Basel on Caspar Bonecurtius, a noble knight stating -

began to lose his mind gradually over a two year period, to such an extent that finally he was completely stupefied and did nothing rationally. He had no desire for food and ate only when forcibly fed. ... Finally after matters had gone on thus for six months, he died.

Further, the autopsy report of Plater stated the following -

a round fleshy tumor, like an acorn. It was hard and full of holes and was as large as a medium-sized apple. It was covered with its own membrane and was entwined with veins. However, it was free of all connections with the matter of the brain, so much so that when it was removed by hand, it left behind a remarkable cavity.

This was the first case in the history that documented a patient with a lesion that was most compatible with a meningioma.

Next, in a contribution by Italian scientists, Paterniti [9] documents the first contribution of Andrea Vacca' Berlinghieri in 1813 in a manuscript *Trattato di Chirurgia Pratica*, which was never published. Its discovery was made accidentally by David Giordano, who referred in detail in an article on surgeon of Pisa in *La chirurgia di Andrea Vacca' Berlinghieri*. *Riv Storia Sci MedNat*. 1927: XVIII (3-4): 75-106. The unpublished manuscript of 488 pages describes that Vacca Berlinhieri proposed and performed a most bold radical operation. After a craniectomy with five or six burr holes on the outskirts of the fungus, the tumor was removed together the dura mater from which it originated, tying the cut vessels.

In 1847, Zanobi Pecchioli, Professor of Clinical Surgery and Operative Medicine at Modena and then at Siena University, published an account of surgeries performed during 16 years, from 1832 to 1847 (16 of the 1524 reported operations involved trephining of the skull). In one of these interventions, he carried out on July 29 1835, in Siena, for the resection of a meningioma, a defined fungus of the duramater. The case was not referred in the literature by Pecchioli but was described by in Pecchioli [10]. Finally, Cushing [11] coined the modern term of "meningioma".

Figure 1: A schematic diagram of different pathways in different meningiomas, as provided by Szulzewsky et al. [14] under CC-BY Attribution 4.0 International license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

1.1.3. Pathophysiology

Meningiomas arise from arachnoidal cap cells, most of which are near the vicinity of the venous sinuses, and this is the site of greatest prevalence for meningioma formation. The dural venous sinuses (also called dural/cerebral/cranial sinuses) are venous sinuses (channels) found between the periosteal and meningeal layers of dura mater in the brain. They receive blood from the cerebral veins, and cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) from the subarachnoid space via arachnoid granulations. They mainly empty into the internal jugular vein. Cranial venous sinuses communicate with veins outside the skull through emissary veins. These communications help to keep the pressure of blood in the sinuses constant. (contributors [12] and Pamir et al. [13]) A schematic diagram for different pathways in different meningiomas has been provided in figure 1.

1.2. Holliday junction recognition protein (HJURP)

Kato et al. [15] identified a novel gene HJURP, whose activation seemed to play a pivotal role in the immortality of cancer cells. It was considered a possible downstream target for ataxia telangiectasia mutated signaling, and its expression was increased by DNA double-strand breaks (DSB). They observed that HJURP was involved in the homologous recombination pathway in the DSB repair process through interaction with hMSH5 and NBS1, which is a part of the MRN protein complex. Further observation was that HJURP formed nuclear foci in cells at S phase and those subjected to DNA

damage. Their, in vitro assays implied that HJURP bound directly to the Holliday junction and rDNA arrays. Treatment of cancer cells with small interfering RNA (siRNA) against HJURP was observed to cause abnormal chromosomal fusions and led to genomic instability and senescence. In addition, HJURP overexpression was observed in a majority of lung cancers. With these evidences, they suggested that HJURP was an indispensable factor for chromosomal stability in immortalized cancer cells and was a potential novel therapeutic target for the development of anticancer drugs.

The centromere is responsible for accurate chromosome segregation. Mammalian centromeres are specified epigenetically, with all active centromeres containing centromere-specific chromatin in which CENP-A replaces histone H3 within the nucleosome. Foltz et al. [16] show that the proteins responsible for assembly of human CENP-A into centromeric nucleosomes during the G1 phase of the cell cycle are distinct from the chromatin assembly factors previously shown to load other histone H3 variants. Further, they demonstrate that prenucleosomal CENP-A is complexed with histone H4, nucleophosmin 1, and HJURP. It was observed that the recruitment of new CENP-A into nucleosomes at replicated centromeres was dependent on HJURP. Recognition by HJURP was mediated through the centromere targeting domain (CATD) of CENP-A, a region that they demonstrated previously to induce a unique conformational rigidity to both the subnucleosomal CENP-A heterotetramer and the corresponding assembled nucleosome. They thus propose HJURP to be a cell-cycle-regulated CENP-A-specific histone chaperone required for centromeric chromatin assembly.

Valente et al. [17] demonstrated that the Holliday Junction Recognizing Protein, a novel DNA repair protein over expressed in lung cancer, was extremely over-expressed in glioblastoma, with a median change of about 134 fold.

Nardi et al. [18] show that HJURP was recruited to centromeres through a direct interaction between the HJURP centromere targeting domain and the Mis18 α - β C-terminal coiled-coil domains. They demonstrated that Mis18 α and Mis18 β formed a heterotetramer through their C-terminal coiled-coil domains. Further, it was observed that Mis18 α - β heterotetramer formation was required for Mis18BP1 binding and centromere recognition. HJURP binding disrupts the Mis18 α - β heterotetramer and removes Mis18 α from centromeres. Thus, they propose stable binding of Mis18 to centromeres in telophase, licenses them for CENP-A deposition. Binding of HJURP deposited CENP-A at centromeres and facilitated the removal of Mis18, restricting CENP-A deposition to a single event per cell cycle.

Finally, recently, Li et al. [1] study the advances in HJURP structure, its function and roles in cancer, in detail.

Many of the different synergies represented as combinations of genes/proteins have been experimentally tested and published. However, there are combinations that have yet to be explored. I address the problem of identifying these unexplored combinations via use of a machine learning based search engine in the next section.

1.3. Insight behind the work

Across all search engines has the fundamental principle remains the same i.e to capture the pattern available in the data and based on that pattern, rank a list of queries. Different algorithms can be applied, however if the fundamental pattern is captured ac-

curately, then the rankings will remain approximately the same, with slight variations, across the different kinds of search engines used. I use one search engine, however, vary the way the patterns are captured via use of different sensitivity methods. Each sensitivity method uses a different flavour/mathematical formulation to compute the sensitivity indices to estimate the influence of the involved factors. These involved factors are genes that play a role in cell biology, in the above research. The insight is that all methods will capture the sensitivity of the involved factors based on their recorded regulations and the search engine will rank the combination of factors based on these sensitivity indices. Since the role of involved factors are captured properly, the search engine will give appropriate rankings to the combinations, thus capturing which gene combinations might be playing significantly in a biological phenomena. The above work shows rankings for experimentally confirmed combinations as well as unexplored/untested combinations. These rankings are not just numbers. They point to the existence of biological synergy in the form of gene combinations, whether tested in wet lab or unexplored till now. Finally, the findings suggest that the rankings are conserved across the different sensitivity methods used.

1.4. Combinatorial search problem and a possible solution

In a recently published work Sinha [3], a frame work of a search engine was developed which can rank combinations of factors (genes/proteins) in a signaling pathway. The work uses SVM package by Joachims [19] in https://www.cs.cornell.edu/people/tj/svm_light/svm_rank.html. I use the adaptation to rank 2^{nd} order gene combinations. The sensitivity package by Pujol et al. [20] was used to develop the search engine pipeline. The current research uses the Hilbert Schmidt Independence Criterion (HSIC) and SOBOL method, implemented in the sensitivity package mentioned above. I use three different kernels under the HSIC method namely, • laplace, • linear and • rbf. For SOBOL method, I use • sobol-2002, and • sobol-jansen. Each of these variants or kernels have been implemented in the sensitivity package and option has been provided in the search engine code to generate the rankings for a particular gene, using a choice of a kernel/variant at a time. Technical details about the variants and kernels can be found in references citetd in Pujol et al. [20].

2. Methods

2.1. Static data from Patel et al. [2]

Patel et al. [2] analyzed 160 meningioma samples from 140 patients, and according to the WHO histopathological classification system for meningioma, they found 121 tumors were of grade I (benign), 32 were of grade II (atypical), and 7 were of grade III (malignant). To determine whether meningiomas could be differentiated based on gene expression profiles, they used principal component analysis (PCA) on a discovery set of 97 tumors (i.e 77 WHO grade I and 20 WHO grade II). Next, they employed nonnegative matrix factorization (NMF) clustering (a unsupervised machine-learning approach) for $k = 2$ to $k = 7$ using the 1,500 genes that varied most among the tumor

samples. They report that after 1,000 iterations, 3 clusters ($k = 3$) emerged as providing the best fit as determined by the consensus membership, cophenetic, and silhouette scores. They evaluated the cluster significance of the 3 subtypes using SigClust (Huang et al. [21]) and observed statistical significance between cluster boundaries, which exhibited significant differences in WHO grade representation.

2.2. Design for static data from Patel et al. [2]

The procedure begins with the listing of all C_k^n combinations for k number of genes from a total of n genes. Here n can be the choice of the biologist. k is ≥ 2 and $\leq (n - 1)$. Each of the combination of order k represent a unique set of interaction between the involved genetic factors. Since the sensitivity analysis methods require a sample for a particular observation, a steep gaussian distribution was generated with a jitter (noise) added to the deviation from the reported point measurement of 0.005. In this experiment, the distribution contained 10 measurements (including the point of measurement under consideration). This is repeated for each point of measurement.

To have an averaged ranking, the experiment was designed to run for 25 iterations. In each iteration, the datasets are combined in a specified format which go as input as per the requirement of a particular sensitivity analysis method. Thus for each p^{th} combination in C_k^n combinations, the dataset is prepared in a required format. Details of formatting the data have not been presented in the article to maintain the fluidity and brevity. Interested readers can find examples of formatting the data in the sensitivity analysis package in R. Sensitivity analysis and its relevance in systems biology have been covered in a recently published article by Sinha [22], which forms the foundation for this work. After the data has been transformed, vectorized programming is employed for density based sensitivity analysis and looping is employed for variance based sensitivity analysis to compute the required sensitivity indices for each of the p combinations.

After the above sensitivity indices have been stored for each of the p^{th} combination, for a chosen sensitivity analysis method, the next step in the design of experiment is conducted. Here, the indices are averaged per combination to have a mean index value. These index values form the discriminative features for a particular combination. For a k^{th} order combination, a vector of k elements or indices forms a feature vector. Thus for C_k^n combinations there will be C_k^n vectors, each containing k elements. Next, SVM_{learn}^{Rank} Joachims [19] is used to generate a model on default value C value of 20. In the current experiment on toy model C value has not been tuned. The training set helps in the generation of the model as the different gene combinations are numbered in order which are used as rank indices. The model is then used to generate score on the observations in the testing set using the $SVM_{classify}^{Rank}$ Joachims [19]. This is followed by sorting of these scores along with the rank indices already assigned to the gene combinations. The end result is a sorted order of the gene combinations based on the ranking score learned by the SVM^{Rank} algorithm.

Note that the following is the order in which the files should be executed in R Team [23], in order, for obtaining the desired results (Note that the code will not be explained here) - • use source("extractMeningiomadata.R") • use source("manuscript-2-2.R") • use source("SVMRank-Results-S-mean.R").

2.3. Translating the pipeline into code of execution in R

The execution begins by some preprocessing of the file containing the information regarding the down regulated genes via `source("extractMeningiomadata.R")`. The library containing the sensitivity analysis methods is then loaded in the interface using the command `library(sensitivity)` (Note - this package can be downloaded for free from <https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/sensitivity/index.html>). Next a gaussian distribution for a particular transcript level for a gene is generated to have a sample. This is needed in the computation of sensitivity index for that particular gene. A gene of particular choice is selected (in blue) and the choice of the combination is made (here $k = 2$). Later a kernel is used (here rbf for HSIC method). 25 different indices are generated which help in generating aggregate rank using these 25 indices. The Support vector ranking algorithm is employed to generate the scores for different combinations and these scores are then sorted out. This is done using the command `source("SVMRank - Results - S - mean.R")`. A file is generated that contains the combinations in increasing order of influence. Note that 1 means lowest rank and vice versa, for 2^{nd} order combinations for any gene using a particular density based sensitivity index.

2.4. Regarding biological insight

For the recorded gene expression values, the sensitivity indices are computed. The search engine uses the kernel based density method. The kernel method takes the data, that is in a lower dimensional plane and projects it to a higher dimensional plane, with an idea that in a higher dimensional place, there exists a dot product between the projected data. To simply state, the idea is that in a higher dimensional plane the nonlinearities between the data (in lower dimensional plane) will be captured and the data may be segregated from each other via a hyperplane. So, irrespective of the method used to measure the gene expression values, if the measurements capture biological information (to whatever extent they can), then the kernel method will be able to capture the nonlinearities/synergies, if existing and allow the sensitivity analysis method (here density based method) to estimate the strength of influence of each of the factors. Based on the sensitivity indices of combinations of a particular order, the search engine ranks the combinations. Details of search engine are provided in the published work in Sinha [3].

It is important to note that the search engine will not give insight about the mechanism of synergy between the components of a combination. However, if the synergy exists between components of an unexplored/untested combination, then the sensitivity indices will capture the influence of these components taken together (which form a combination of interest) and will rank the combination appropriately. These rankings provide insight about which combination a biologist/oncologist might want to test in a forest of combinations for a given scenario in a cell (whether normal or pathological).

3. Results & Discussion

3.1. HJURP related synergies

Note - HJURP was found to be upregulated in Type C. Upregulation was defined as Type logFC to be > 1 and $FDR \leq 0.001$, in Patel et al. [2]. Also, sorting of scores by the machine learning algorithm were done in ascending order, i.e - top is lowest in ranking. A total of 258 2^{nd} order combinations of HJURP were recorded.

3.1.1. FOXM1/WNT signaling target genes in Vasudevan et al. [4]

Meningioma is the most common primary intracranial tumor, but the molecular drivers of aggressive meningioma are incompletely understood. Using 280 human meningioma samples and RNA sequencing, immunohistochemistry, whole-exome sequencing, DNA methylation arrays, and targeted gene expression profiling, Vasudevan et al. [4] defined the molecular profile of aggressive meningioma. Their transcriptomic analyses identified FOXM1 as a key transcription factor for meningioma proliferation and a marker of poor clinical outcomes, while they discovered genomic and epigenomic factors associated with FOXM1 activation in aggressive meningiomas. Finally, they defined a FOXM1/WNT signaling axis in meningioma that was associated with a mitotic gene expression program, poor clinical outcomes, and proliferation of primary meningioma cells.

Vasudevan et al. [4] provide a set of FOXM1 target genes in meningioma and they also defined a FOXM1/WNT signaling axis in meningioma that was associated with a mitotic gene expression program, poor clinical outcomes, and proliferation of primary meningioma cells. Of these, CDC28 protein kinase regulatory subunit 2 (CKS2), TPX2 microtubule nucleation factor (TPX2), DNA topoisomerase II alpha (TOP2A), cyclin B2 (CCNB2), cell division cycle associated 5 (CDCA5), trophinin associated protein (TROAP), thymidine kinase 1 (TK1), BUB1 mitotic checkpoint serine/threonine kinase B (BUB1B), centromere protein F (CENPF), SPC25 component of NDC80 kinetochore complex (SPC25), kinesin family member 4A (KIF4A), NIMA related kinase 2 (NEK2), kinesin family member 18B (KIF18B), BRCA1 interacting DNA helicase 1 (BRIP1) and DEP domain containing 1B (DEPDC1B), were found to be upregulated in Patel et al. [2].

Using the adaptation of the above mentioned search engine, I was able to rank 2^{nd} order combination of HJURP with these genes.

Table 1 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 2 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 1. The table 1 shows rankings of individual members w.r.t HJURP. CCNB2 - HJURP shows high ranking of, 62, 236 (linear), 192 (rbf), 225 (jansen); NEK2 - HJURP shows high ranking of, 123, 160 (linear), 229 (rbf), 252 (jansen); and KIF18B - HJURP shows high ranking of, 195 (laplace), 225 (linear), 197 (rbf), 42.

While, CKS2 - HJURP shows low ranking of, 114, 150, 147, 241; TPX2 - HJURP shows low ranking of, 137, 170, 54, 45; TOP2A - HJURP shows low ranking of, 121, 75, 237, 219; CDCA5 - HJURP shows low ranking of, 153, 41, 120, 69; TROAP - HJURP shows low ranking of, 205, 112, 151, 7; TK1 - HJURP shows low ranking of,

82, 56, 59, 54; BUB1B - HJURP shows low ranking of, 69, 177, 16, 90; CENPF - HJURP shows low ranking of, 130, 99, 102, 200; SPC25 - HJURP shows low ranking of, 112, 181, 115, 68; KIF4A - HJURP shows low ranking of, 210, 138, 96, 192; BRIP1 - HJURP shows low ranking of, 79, 108, 90, 34; and DEPDC1B - HJURP shows low ranking of, 41, 58, 38, 56.

RANKING INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS VS HJURP				
RANKING OF INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS W.R.T HJURP				
	laplace	linear	rbf	jansen
CKS2 - HJURP	114	150	147	241
TPX2 - HJURP	137	170	54	45
TOP2A - HJURP	121	75	237	219
CCNB2 - HJURP	62	236	192	225
CDCA5 - HJURP	153	41	120	69
TROAP - HJURP	205	112	151	7
TK1 - HJURP	82	56	59	54
BUB1B - HJURP	69	177	16	90
CENPF - HJURP	130	99	102	200
SPC25 - HJURP	112	181	115	68
KIF4A - HJURP	210	138	96	192
NEK2 - HJURP	123	160	229	252
KIF18B - HJURP	195	225	197	42
BRIP1 - HJURP	79	108	90	34
DEPDC1B - HJURP	41	58	38	56

Table 1: 2^{nd} order interaction ranking between HJURP VS Individual members.

One can also interpret the results of the table 1 graphically, with the following influences - • Individual members w.r.t HJURP with HJURP – > CKS2 / TOP2A / CCNB2 / TROAP / TK1.

3.1.2. HJURP unknown combinations with high ranking

Along with the above known genes affected by HJURP, there are others genes that were upregulated and recorded in Patel et al. [2]. i document here, the 2^{nd} order combinations with HJURP, which were assigned high rank by the machine learning based search engine. These high ranks point to the possible existence of synergy between the

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES	
Individual members w.r.t HJURP	
CCNB2	HJURP
NEK2	HJURP
KIF18B	HJURP

Table 2: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between HJURP and Individual members.

HJURP and the genetic factors, that might not have been explored till now. Further, wet lab tests will confirm the veracity of these rankings.

Of these, reticulocalbin 1 (RCN1), centromere protein M (CENPM), G protein-coupled receptor 83 (GPR83), H1.3 linker histone, cluster member (HIST1H1D), egl-9 family hypoxia inducible factor 3 (EGLN3), HIG1 hypoxia inducible domain family member 1B (HIGD1B), creatine kinase, mitochondrial 2 (CKMT2), doublecortin like kinase 1 (DCLK1), desmoglein 1 (DSG1), desmocollin 3 (DSC3), Rap guanine nucleotide exchange factor 5 (RAPGEF5), lysyl oxidase like 4 (LOXL4), pleckstrin homology like domain family A member 1 (PHLDA1), TOPBP1 interacting checkpoint and replication regulator (TICRR), MARVEL domain containing 3 (MARVELD3), mitogen-activated protein kinase 4 (MAPK4), denticleless E3 ubiquitin protein ligase homolog (DTL), cell division cycle associated 7 (CDCA7), solute carrier family 22 member 8 (SLC22A8), oleoyl-ACP hydrolase (OLAH), solute carrier family 16 member 12 (SLC16A12), pantothenate kinase 1 (PANK1), pleckstrin homology and RhoGEF domain containing G4B (PLEKHG4B), PDCD10 and GCKIII kinases associated 1 (C4orf19), coiled-coil domain containing 144C, pseudogene (CCDC144CP), diacylglycerol kinase iota (DGKI), H2B clustered histone 5 (HIST1H2BD), cell division cycle 25C (CDC25C), H4 clustered histone 8 (HIST1H4H), zinc finger protein 233 (ZNF233), coiled-coil domain containing 78 (CCDC78), solute carrier family 9 member C2 (putative) (SLC9C2), maternal embryonic leucine zipper kinase (MELK), insulin like growth factor 2 (IGF2), ETS variant transcription factor 4 (ETV4), DnaJ heat shock protein family (Hsp40) member C22 (DNAJC22), carbonic anhydrase 8 (CA8), apolipoprotein L domain containing 1 (APOLD1), H2A clustered histone 6 (HIST1H2AC), H2B clustered histone 4 (HIST1H2BC), RNF32 divergent transcript (LINC01006), immunoglobulin superfamily member 5 (IGSF5), IZUMO1 receptor, JUNO (IZUMO1R), long intergenic non-protein coding RNA 482 (LINC00482), NDUF4A mitochondrial complex associated like 2 (NDUFA4L2), H1.2 linker histone, cluster member (HIST1H1C), smoothelin like 2 (SMTNL2), solute carrier family 38 member 3 (SLC38A3), apolipoprotein D (APOD), solute carrier family 30 member 10 (SLC30A10), hydroxycarboxylic acid receptor 1 (HCAR1), protocadherin gamma subfamily A, 1 (PCDHGA1), fire intergenic repeating RNA element (FIRRE), killer cell lectin like receptor K1 (KLRK1), long intergenic non-protein coding RNA 887 (LINC00887), lipocalin like 1 (LCNL1), reticulocalbin 1 pseudogene 2 (RCN1P2),

long intergenic non-protein coding RNA 954 (LINC00954), MIR181A1 host gene (MIR181A1HG), NALCN antisense RNA 1 (NALCN-AS1), NADH:ubiquinone oxidoreductase subunit B1 pseudogene 2 (NDUFB1P2), small regulatory polypeptide of amino acid response (SPAAR), cytochrome c oxidase subunit 5B pseudogene 6 (COX5BP6), uroplakin 3B (UPK3B), long intergenic non-protein coding RNA 1948 (LINC01948) and high mobility group box 1 pseudogene 21 (HMGB1P21), were found to be recorded as upregulated in data by Patel et al. [2]. Using the adaptation of the above mentioned search engine, I was able to rank 2nd order combination of HJURP with these genes.

Table 3 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 4 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 3. The table 3 shows rankings of individual members w.r.t HJURP.

RANKING UNKNOWN INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS VS HJURP									
RANKING OF UNKNOWN INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS W.R.T HJURP									
	laplace	linear	rbf	jansen		laplace	linear	rbf	jansen
RCN1 - HJURP	174	78	243	161	CENPM - HJURP	89	183	210	149
GPR83 - HJURP	223	200	221	62	HIST1H1D - HJURP	190	184	168	188
EGLN3 - HJURP	258	220	219	120	HIGD1B - HJURP	192	185	194	235
CKMT2 - HJURP	158	191	230	57	DCLK1 - HJURP	197	228	227	172
DSG1 - HJURP	237	237	231	96	DSC3 - HJURP	240	255	249	117
RAPGEF5 - HJURP	221	223	169	110	LOXL4 - HJURP	207	222	177	151
PHLDA1 - HJURP	244	257	214	112	TICRR - HJURP	189	188	107	189
MARVELD3 - HJURP	255	254	252	126	MAPK4 - HJURP	247	245	257	122
DTL - HJURP	182	158	228	3	CDCA7 - HJURP	206	241	254	193
SLC22A8 - HJURP	245	258	256	137	OLAH - HJURP	161	161	71	199
SLC16A12 - HJURP	250	252	258	124	PANK1 - HJURP	236	246	209	46
PLEKHG4B - HJURP	257	215	220	150	C4orf19 - HJURP	204	205	241	118
CCDC144CP - HJURP	218	231	140	163	DGKI - HJURP	184	167	198	177
HIST1H2BD - HJURP	148	247	212	135	CDC25C - HJURP	191	95	160	220
HIST1H4H - HJURP	196	202	201	78	ZNF233 - HJURP	177	213	186	108
CCDC78 - HJURP	235	159	187	61	SLC9C2 - HJURP	224	253	217	102
MELK - HJURP	119	180	155	213	IGF2 - HJURP	243	164	226	87
ETV4 - HJURP	199	194	153	30	DNAJC22 - HJURP	248	251	247	145
CA8 - HJURP	256	212	248	136	APOLD1 - HJURP	202	244	123	246
HIST1H2AC - HJURP	211	214	245	66	HIST1H2BC - HJURP	180	133	176	197
LINC01006 - HJURP	220	239	222	73	IGSF5 - HJURP	242	227	205	169
IZUMO1R - HJURP	187	230	202	111	LINC00482 - HJURP	193	243	238	81
NDUFA4L2 - HJURP	176	165	162	109	HIST1H1C - HJURP	201	217	191	75
SMTNL2 - HJURP	253	256	253	113	SLC38A3 - HJURP	249	198	239	99
APOD - HJURP	251	210	215	74	SLC30A10 - HJURP	234	238	255	101
HCAR1 - HJURP	241	226	172	155	PCDHGA1 - HJURP	140	189	235	233
FIRRE - HJURP	238	190	242	142	KLRK1 - HJURP	200	229	232	141
LINC00887 - HJURP	216	221	208	70	LCNL1 - HJURP	227	240	204	119
RCN1P2 - HJURP	198	235	78	170	LINC00954 - HJURP	212	153	250	133
MIR181A1HG - HJURP	217	92	199	243	NALCN.AS1 - HJURP	155	193	113	203
NDUFB1P2 - HJURP	124	195	170	255	SPAAR - HJURP	154	162	183	254
COX5BP6 - HJURP	230	155	224	52	UPK3B - HJURP	209	234	207	97
LINC01948 - HJURP	159	242	86	247	HMGB1P21 - HJURP	106	172	154	183

Table 3: 2nd order interaction ranking between HJURP VS Individual members.

One can also interpret the results of the table 3 graphically, with the following influences - • Individual members w.r.t HJURP with HJURP – > RCN1 / CENPM / GPR83 / HIST1H1D / EGLN3 / HIGD1B / CKMT2 / DCLK1 / DSG1 / DSC3 / RAPGEF5 / LOXL4 / PHLDA1 / TICRR / MARVELD3 / MAPK4 / DTL / CDCA7 / SLC22A8

/ OLAH / SLC16A12 / PANK1 / PLEKHG4B / C4orf19 / CCDC144CP / DGKI / HIST1H2BD / CDC25C / HIST1H4H / ZNF233 / CCDC78 / SLC9C2 / MELK / IGF2 / ETV4 / DNAJC22 / CA8 / APOLD1 / HIST1H2AC / HIST1H2BC / LINC01006 / IGSF5 / IZUMO1R / LINC00482 / NDUFA4L2 / HIST1H1C / SMTNL2 / SLC38A3 / APOD / SLC30A10 / HCAR1 / PCDHGA1 / FIRRE / KLRK1 / LINC00887 / LCNL1 / RCN1P2 / LINC00954 / MIR181A1HG / NALCN.AS1 / NDUFB1P2 / SPAAR / COX5BP6 / UPK3B / LINC01948 / HMGB1P21.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES

Unknown Individual members w.r.t HJURP	
RCN1 / CENPM / GPR83 / HIST1H1D / EGLN3 / ...	
HIGD1B / CKMT2 / DCLK1 / DSG1 / DSC3 / ...	
RAPGEF5 / LOXL4 / PHLDA1 / TICRR / MARVELD3 / ...	
MAPK4 / DTL / CDCA7 / SLC22A8 / OLAH / SLC16A12 / ...	
PANK1 / PLEKHG4B / C4orf19 / CCDC144CP / DGKI / ...	
HIST1H2BD / CDC25C / HIST1H4H / ZNF233 / CCDC78 / ...	
SLC9C2 / MELK / IGF2 / ETV4 / DNAJC22 / CA8 / ...	
APOLD1 / HIST1H2AC / HIST1H2BC / LINC01006 / IGSF5 / ...	
IZUMO1R / LINC00482 / NDUFA4L2 / HIST1H1C / SMTNL2 / ...	
SLC38A3 / APOD / SLC30A10 / HCAR1 / PCDHGA1 / FIRRE / ...	
KLRK1 / LINC00887 / LCNL1 / RCN1P2 / LINC00954 / ...	
MIR181A1HG / NALCN.AS1 / NDUFB1P2 / SPAAR / COX5BP6 / ...	
UPK3B / LINC01948 / HMGB1P21	HJURP

Table 4: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between HJURP and Individual members.

4. Conclusion

Presented here are a range of multiple synergistic HJURP 2nd order combinations that were ranked via a machine learning based search engine. Via majority voting across the ranking methods, it was possible to find plausible unexplored synergistic combinations of HJURP-X that might be prevalent in meningioma.

Conflict of interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

Author's contributions

Concept, design, in silico implementation - SS. Analysis and interpretation of results - SS. Manuscript writing - SS. Manuscript revision - SS. Approval of manuscript - SS

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Source of Data

Data used in this research work was released in a publication in Patel et al. [2]. Permission to use, granted by PNAS.

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